

A Cross-Sectional Study of Awareness & Consumption Pattern of Millets among Women in Udaipur**Vikram Singh¹, Anjili Mathur², Shruti Priyadarshini³, Jatin Prajapati⁴, Shivani Vihan⁵, Shubham Mittal⁶**¹MD (Community Medicine), Deputy Chief Medical and Health Officer (Dy CMHO), Udaipur, Government of Rajasthan, India²Senior Professor, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India³MBBS, MD (Radiodiagnosis)^{4,5,6}PG student, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

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Corresponding author: Dr. Jatin Prajapati

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Abstract**Background:** Millets, often termed “nutri-cereals,” are rich in nutrients, environmentally sustainable, and suitable for cultivation in low-input agricultural systems. Despite their benefits, millet consumption has declined in urban India. Women, as key decision-makers in household diets, play a crucial role in influencing food choices.**Objectives:** To evaluate the level of awareness, types of millets consumed, frequency and methods of consumption, and socio-demographic factors influencing millet awareness among women in Udaipur.**Methods:** A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted over six months (Nov 2023–April 2024) among 120 women aged ≥ 18 years residing in the Urban Health Training Center (UHTC) field practice area, Dhanmandi, Udaipur. A semi-structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Sampling involved simple random selection of streets followed by systematic selection of households. Data were analyzed using SPSS; chi-square test was used for categorical data, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.**Results:** The mean age of participants was 39.3 ± 13.62 years. Most were Hindu (80.8%), homemakers (83.3%), and belonged to the lower-middle socio-economic class (56.6%). Awareness of millets was reported by 63.3% of participants. Religion ($p=0.00001$), socio-economic status ($p=0.0008$), dietary habits ($p=0.000012$), and lifestyle ($p=0.035$) were significantly associated with millet awareness. Among those aware, barnyard millet (93.4%) and foxtail millet (82.9%) were most commonly consumed. Khichdi (97.4%) and rab (72.3%) were the most frequently prepared millet dishes. Boiling (94.7%) was the predominant method of preparation. Only 2.3% consumed millets daily; most (41.9%) consumed them weekly.**Conclusion:** Although awareness of millets was moderate, regular consumption remains low. Socio-cultural and dietary factors significantly influence awareness and consumption patterns. Targeted nutrition education and improved availability of millet-based products could enhance their integration into urban diets, supporting both public health and sustainable agriculture.**Keywords:** Millets, Awareness, Consumption Pattern, Women, Udaipur, Dietary Habits, Nutritional Awareness.

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Introduction

Millets are a group of highly variable small seeded grasses, widely grown around the world as cereal crops or grains for fodder and human food.[1] These are highly nutritious and can be cultivated in marginal or low-fertility soils with minimal inputs, such as fertilizers and pesticides. These crops play a significant role in ensuring food and nutritional security in the country. Most millet crops are indigenous to India and are commonly referred to as “Nutri-cereals” because they provide essential

nutrients required for the human body. Millets are rain-fed crops, thriving in areas with low rainfall, making them vital for sustainable agriculture and food security.[2] Based on the area cultivated and grain size, millets are classified as major and minor millets. Major millets include sorghum (jowar) and pearl millet (bajra), while minor millets comprise finger millet (ragi/mandua), foxtail millet (kangni/Italian millet), little millet (kutki), kodo millet, barnyard millet (sawan/jhangora), proso

millet (cheena/common millet), and brown top millet (korale). In some African countries, other millets like fonio and tef are also grown.

Millets were among the first crops domesticated by humans in Asia and Africa and later became essential food sources for civilizations worldwide. These crops have a short growing cycle, completing their lifecycle in 2-4 months, and are well-suited to diverse cropping systems.[3] They are also highly adaptable to changing environmental conditions, especially during unpredictable monsoon patterns.

In addition to their health benefits, millets are environmentally sustainable due to their resilience to drought and low water requirements, making them an ideal crop for arid regions like Rajasthan.[4] The nutritional benefits of millets, rich in proteins, essential amino acids, minerals, and dietary fibre, are also crucial for addressing micronutrient deficiencies prevalent in many populations.[5] However, in recent decades, the cultivation and consumption of millets have declined significantly. This is largely attributed to the Green Revolution, which emphasized high-yielding varieties of rice and wheat, overshadowing millets. Furthermore, urbanization and changing food habits have shifted preferences toward convenience foods, often sidelining traditional staples like millets.

In Udaipur, a region with a strong agricultural base, millets were once a dietary mainstay but are now less commonly consumed. Women, who play a central role in household nutrition, are key to understanding this shift. Despite government efforts like the National Year of Millets (2018) and the International Year of Millets (2023), awareness about the nutritional and health benefits of millets remains limited. Factors such as perceptions of millets as “poor man’s food,” the time-consuming nature of their preparation, and competition from processed foods have contributed to their reduced popularity.

Economic considerations also play a role; rice and wheat are more affordable and readily available due to government subsidies and procurement policies. Moreover, urbanization has introduced dietary diversification, with households increasingly opting for high-value foods like dairy, fruits, and processed snacks. These changing consumption patterns have led to a notable decline in millet-based meals, even among rural households.

Research on women’s awareness and consumption patterns of millets in Udaipur is crucial to understanding these dynamics and promoting millets as a staple. Women’s knowledge and perceptions significantly influence household food choices, making them pivotal in dietary transitions.

Studies indicate that many women lack awareness of millets’ nutritional benefits and their role in preventing lifestyle diseases like diabetes and cardiovascular issues. Enhancing their knowledge and addressing barriers such as convenience and market availability can drive a resurgence in millet consumption. By identifying gaps in awareness and promoting millet-based value-added products, policymakers and health advocates can integrate these grains into modern diets. This not only supports public health objectives but also fosters agricultural sustainability by encouraging the cultivation of millets, benefiting smallholder farmers in Udaipur and beyond.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was population-based cross-sectional study.

Study Area: This study was conducted in field practice area of the Urban Health Training Center (UHTC), Dhanmandi, affiliated with the Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, and Rajasthan.

Sample Size Calculation: The sample size was calculated using the formula:

$$N = Z^2 P(1-P)/L^2$$

Where:

- $Z = 1.96$ (value for 95% confidence interval)
- $P = 79\%$ (proportion of awareness about millets as reported in the study “Awareness and Consumption of Millets by Women in Coimbatore City” by Kalaiselvi et al.[6])
- $L =$ The Precision of estimate

$$10\% \text{ of } 79 = 7.9$$

The calculation was as follows:

$$3.84 * 79 * 21 / 7.9 * 7.9 = 103$$

Taking 10% as dropout rate, sample size becomes 114 and after round of, we studied 120 participants in this study.

Study Duration: The study was conducted for a period of 6 months from Nov 2023 to April 2024.

Study subjects:

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Women aged 18 years and above residing in the field practice area of UHTC.
2. Women willing to participate and provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Women below 18 years of age.
2. Women unwilling to participate in the study.

Data Collection Tools and Techniques:

a) A semi-structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Interviews were conducted in the field practice area of UHTC.

b) Streets were selected using simple random sampling. Within each street, households were chosen using systematic sampling, selecting every fourth household until the sample size was achieved, with 10 households per street.

Study Variables:

- **Age:** Recorded in completed years.
- **Occupation and Education:** Defined using standard social classifications and Census of India guidelines, respectively.
- **Socioeconomic Status (SES):** Determined using the Modified BG Prasad classification updated for 2023 based on per capita monthly income.
- **Body Mass Index (BMI):** Categorized as per WHO standards.
- **Dietary Habits:** Included vegetarian and non-vegetarian preferences.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using statistical software. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ±standard deviation and compared using the Student’s t-test. Categorical data were presented as proportions and analyzed using the chi-square test. A confidence level of 95% was used, with p-values <0.05 considered statistically significant. Odds ratios for risk factors were calculated using a 2x2 table.

Ethical Consideration:

1. Approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of RNT Medical College, Udaipur.
2. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection.
3. Interviews were conducted privately to ensure confidentiality and anonymity.
4. All personal identifiers were removed from datasets to maintain data privacy.

Results

The study included 120 participants, with a mean age of 39.3 ±13.62 years. The majority of the participants (35%) were in the 18-30 years age group, followed by 26.7% in 31-40 years, and smaller proportions in older age groups. Most participants were Hindu (80.8%), with Muslims (15%) and Jains (4.2%) forming the remaining religious groups. Regarding education, 44.2% had completed secondary education, followed by 24% with primary education. A significant proportion of participants were homemakers (83.3%), while 11.7% were employed in the private sector, and 3.3% were engaged in business.[Table 1]

In terms of family structure, more than half of the participants (56.7%) lived in nuclear families, while 35.8% lived in joint families, and 7.5% in three-generation households. The majority were married (93.3%), with 5% widowed and 1.7% unmarried. Socio-economically, 56.6% belonged to the lower middle class, 25% to the middle class, and 11.7% to the upper middle class, while only 6.7% were from the lower class. No participants belonged to the upper class.[Table 1]

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of participants

Variables		Number (N=120)	Percentage	
Age group (in years)	18-30	42	35	Mean ± SD = 39.3±13.62
	31-40	32	26.7	
	41-50	19	15.8	
	51-60	16	13.3	
	>60	11	9.2	
Religion	Hindu	97	80.8	
	Muslim	18	15	
	Jain	5	4.2	
Education	No Formal Education	11	9.2	
	Primary	30	24	
	Secondary	53	44.2	
	Senior Secondary	2	1.7	
	Graduation	23	19.2	
	Professional	1	0.8	
Occupation	Homemaker	100	83.3	
	Private	14	11.7	
	Business	4	3.3	
	Others	2	1.7	
Type of Family	Nuclear	68	56.7	
	Joint	43	35.8	
	Three generation	9	7.5	

Marital Status	Married	112	93.3
	Unmarried	2	1.7
	Widow	6	5
Socio-economic Status	Lower	8	6.7
	Lower Middle	68	56.6
	Middle	30	25
	Upper Middle	14	11.7
	Upper	0	0

Figure 1: Distribution of participants according to BMI

The mean height and weight of the female participants were 151.52 ± 13.43 cm and 58.8 ± 10.81 kg, respectively. Based on BMI distribution, nearly half of the participants (47.5%) had a normal BMI (18.5–24.9 kg/m²), while 32.5% were overweight (25–29.9 kg/m²) and 15.8% were obese (≥30 kg/m²). Only 4.2% of the participants were underweight (<18.5 kg/m²).

This indicates a substantial proportion of the participants were either overweight or obese. (Figure 1) The study assessed awareness about millets among participants, finding that 63.3% (76) were aware, while 36.7% (44) were not. Age group did not show a statistically significant association with millet awareness (p = 0.572). Similarly, education level did not significantly affect awareness (p = 0.93). However, religion had a highly significant association (p = 0.00001), with

most Hindus (74.2%) being aware, compared to only 5.5% of Muslims. Socio-economic status also showed a significant association (p = 0.0008), with higher awareness among participants from the lower and lower-middle classes compared to those from the upper-middle class. (Table 2) Lifestyle and dietary habits were significantly associated with millet awareness.

Participants with a sedentary lifestyle were more aware (72.2%) compared to those with a moderate lifestyle (56.1%, p = 0.035). Dietary habits showed a highly significant association (p = 0.000012), with vegetarians having much higher awareness (72.9%) than non-vegetarians (25%). These results indicate that religion, socio-economic status, lifestyle, and dietary habits play crucial roles in determining millet awareness among the participants. (Table 2)

Table 2: Correlation of various variables and awareness about millets

Variables		Awareness about Millets			Remarks
		Yes (N=76)	No (N=44)	Total (N=120)	
Age group (in years)	18-30	24(57.1)	18(42.9)	42(100)	Chi square = 2.915 df= 4 P value= 0.572
	31-40	24(75)	8(25)	32(100)	
	41-50	12(63.2)	7(36.8)	19(100)	
	51-60	9(56.3)	7(43.7)	16(100)	
	>60	7(63.6)	4(36.4)	11(100)	
Religion	Hindu	72(74.2)	25(25.8)	97(100)	Chi square = 30.856

	Muslim	1(5.5)	17(94.5)	18(100)	df= 2
	Jain	3(60)	2(40)	5(100)	P value= 0.00001*
Education	No Formal Education	6(54.5)	5(45.5)	11(100)	Chi square = 2.33
	Primary	20(66.7)	10(33.3)	30(100)	df= 5
	Secondary	33(62.2)	20(37.8)	53(100)	P value= 0.8015
	Senior Secondary	2(100)	0(0)	2(100)	
	Graduation	14(60.9)	9(39.1)	23(100)	
	Professional	1(100)	0(0)	1(100)	
Socio-economic Status	Lower	6(75)	2(25)	8(100)	Chi square = 16.66
	Lower Middle	48(70.6)	20(29.4)	68(100)	df= 4
	Middle	20(66.6)	10(33.4)	30(100)	P value= 0.0008*
	Upper Middle	2(14.3)	12(85.7)	14(100)	
	Upper	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	
Lifestyle	Sedentary	39(72.2)	15(27.8)	54(100)	Chi square = 3.34
	Moderate	37(56.1)	29(43.9)	66(100)	df= 1
Dietary Habits	Vegetarian	70(72.9)	26(27.1)	96(100)	Chi square = 18.98
	Non-vegetarian	6(25)	18(75)	24(100)	df= 1
*Highly significant					

In our study we asked females about type of millets consumed by them. Millets consumed by participants were Sorghum (Jowar), Pearl millet (Bajra), Finger millet (Ragi), Ramdana, Barnyard millet (Sawan), Foxtail millet (Kangni) and proso millet (Cheena). Out of 76 females consuming millets, most of females were consuming Barnyard millet 71(93.4%), followed by Foxtail millet 63(82.9%), Pearl millet 51(67.1%), Finger millet 43(56.5%), Sorghum 25(32.9%), Ramdana 21(27.6%) and Proso millet 1(1.3%) while no one was consuming little millets, Kodo millet.

Traditionally cooked recipes of millets were Roti, Sogra, Dalia, Halwa, Khichdi, Upma, Rab and Ghat. Out of 76 females consuming millets, most of

females were cooking recipes like Khichdi 74(97.4%), followed by Rab 55(72.3%), Upma 39(51.3%), Dalia 37(48.6%), Ghat 36(47.4%), Roti 33(43.4%), Halwa 17(22.3%), Sogra 4(5.2%).

Preparation methods of millets were making Roti, sprouting, boiling, roasting, steaming and frying. Out of 76 females consuming millets, most of female's cooking method was boiling 72(94.7%), followed by making Roti 36(47.3%), roasting 27(35.5%), sprouting 24(31.5%), steaming 24(30.3%), frying 6(7.9%). Most of the females i.e. 41.9% were consuming millets once a week, 37.2% females were consuming it during fast. 18.6% were consuming it once a month. Only 2.3% women were consuming it daily. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Distribution of participants based on frequency of consumption of millet (N=76)

Discussion

Millets are often referred to as smart food which is “good for the individual” (nutritious and healthy), “good for the planet” (environmentally sustainable), and “good for the farmer” (resilient). Women are central actors in achieving better household nutrition. Hence this study was conducted among 120 females to analyse their knowledge, attitude and consumption pattern of millets.

In our study, the majority of participants (35%) were aged 18-30 years, followed by those aged 31-40 years (26.7%) and 41-50 years (15.8%), with only 9.2% above 60 years. Similarly, studies by Adithya Girijavallabhan et al. [7] and Sangeetha et al. [8] reported that 50% of subjects were under 30 years. Regarding religion, 80.8% of participants were Hindu, 15% Muslim, and 4.2% Jain, reflecting the urban population distribution in Udaipur (Census 2011: 72% Hindu and 15% Muslim). However, Adithya Girijavallabhan et al. [7] and Sangeetha et al. [8] reported a higher proportion of Hindus (92.3%) in their studies. In terms of education, 44.2% of females in our study were educated up to the secondary level, 24% up to primary/upper primary, and 19.2% were graduates, with only one professional and two educated up to senior secondary. This is consistent with Sripriya Shaji et al. [9], where most females had secondary education, but contrasts with Sangeetha et al. [8], where 40.6% of mothers had primary education, and Adithya Girijavallabhan et al. [7], where most females were college students.

In our study, the majority of females consumed barnyard millet (93.4%), followed by foxtail millet (82.9%), pearl millet (67.1%), finger millet (56.5%), sorghum (32.9%), ramdana (27.6%), and proso millet (1.3%). Traditional millet-based recipes included khichdi (97.4%), rab (72.3%), upma (51.3%), dalia (48.6%), ghat (47.4%), roti (43.4%), halwa (22.3%), and sogra (5.2%). Similar findings were observed in studies by Senthamarai Selvi et al., [10] where porridge was the most common millet product (43.3%), and Adithya Girijavallabhan et al., [7] which highlighted khichdi (16%), roti (25%), and snacks (20%) as common millet-based foods. The preferred preparation methods in our study were boiling (94.7%), followed by making roti (47.3%), roasting (35.5%), sprouting (31.5%), steaming (30.3%), and frying (7.9%), consistent with findings by Adithya Girijavallabhan et al. [7] and Senthamarai Selvi et al., [10] who also reported boiling as the most preferred method.

Regarding consumption frequency, 53.9% of females consumed millets at least once a week, 42.1% consumed them during fasting, and 21.1% consumed them at least once a month, while only

2.6% consumed millets daily. These findings align with Thodeti Manasa et al., [11] where 53% of respondents consumed millets twice a week, and Gomanth Kumar K et al., [12] who reported 39.16% of respondents consuming millets twice weekly. Kane-Potaka et al. [13] also observed that 49.6% consumed millets one or more times per week, while 34.9% rarely consumed them. Similarly, Lakshmy Priya et al. [14] noted equal proportions of respondents consuming millets 1–3 times weekly (41%) or monthly (41%), with only 9% reporting daily consumption, highlighting the overall low daily intake of millets.

Conclusion

The study highlights a moderate level of awareness and consumption of millets among urban women in Udaipur. While nearly two-thirds of participants were aware of millets, actual daily consumption remained low. Millet consumption was significantly influenced by religion, socio-economic status, lifestyle, and dietary habits. Barnyard and foxtail millets were the most commonly consumed, with khichdi and rab being popular preparations. Boiling was the most preferred cooking method. Despite growing awareness, there is a need to promote regular inclusion of millets in daily diets through targeted nutrition education and community-based interventions to enhance health and nutritional security.

References

1. Dayakar Rao B, Bhaskarachary K, Arlene Christina GD, Sudha Devi G, Vilas AT, Tonapi A. Nutritional and health benefits of millets. ICAR Indian Institute of Millets Research (IIMR) Rajendranagar, Hyderabad. 2017;2
2. Amadou I, Gounga ME, Le GW. Millets, nutritional composition, some health benefits and processing. Emir J Food Agric. 2013; 25(7):501-8.
3. VenkateshBhat B, DayakarRao B, Tonapi VA, editors. The story of millets. Bengaluru (India): Karnataka State Department of Agriculture; 2018. Inputs from: Prabhakar, B.Boraiah and Ganiger PC.
4. Vetriventhan M, Azevedo VCR, Upadhyaya HD, et al. Genetic and genomic resources, and breeding for accelerating improvement of small millets: current status and future interventions. Nucleus. 2020; 63:217-239. doi:10.1007/s13237-020-00322-3
5. Chandrakanth MG, Akarsha BM. Green Development for Sustainable Agriculture. FKCCI J Karnataka. 2011.
6. Kalaiselvi M, Fathima P, Parameswari M. Awareness and consumption of millets by women: a study on Coimbatore city. Indian J

- Appl Res. 2016 Feb [cited 2024 Aug 11]. Available from: [https://www.worldwidejournals.com/indian-journal-of-applied-research-\(IJAR\)/recent_issues_pdf/2016/February/February_2016_1454142343_27.pdf](https://www.worldwidejournals.com/indian-journal-of-applied-research-(IJAR)/recent_issues_pdf/2016/February/February_2016_1454142343_27.pdf)
7. Girijavallabhan A, Mathew A, Rajeev G, Thomas S, Premagowri B. Engineering and Technology Impact Factor 7.105. IARJSET Int Adv Res J Sci. 2022; 9(1). Available from: <https://iarjset.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/IARJSET.2022.9127>.
 8. Sangeetha U, Mounika D, Sireesha G. Assessment of Millets Consumption among Young Females (18-23 Years) in Tirupati. J Pharm Negat Results. 2022; 13(Special Issue 7).
 9. Shaji S, Suhaila F, Jabir F, James J, Saju L, George MP, et al. Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) Pertaining to Millets Among Nutrition Practitioners in Kerala. FoodSci Indian J Res Food Sci Nutr. 2024; 11(1):25-31.
 10. Selvi SL, Malathi D. Consumption pattern and nutritional assessment of minor millets among rural women in Madurai District of Tamil Nadu. Int J Curr Microbiol App Sci. 2019; 8(11):2102-2112. doi:10.20546/ijcmas.2019.811.244
 11. Manasa T, Prasad NVVSD, Prathyusha N. Study on millets consumption patterns and awareness of its health benefits among adolescents of Prakasam district, Andhra Pradesh. Pharma Innov J. 2024; 13(4):167-169.
 12. Kumar G, Chandrakumar D, Shanthasheela M, Anandhi V. Awareness and consumption of millet products among college students in YSR (Kadapa) district, Andhra Pradesh. Madras Agric J. 2023; 110(sept):1.
 13. Kane-Potaka J, Anitha S, Tsusaka TW, Botha R, Budumuru M, Upadhyay S, et al. Assessing millets and sorghum consumption behavior in urban India: a large-scale survey. Front Sustain Food Syst. 2021;5:680777.doi:10.3389/fsufs.2021.680777
 14. Krishnamurthy LP, Shanmugam S, Vasudevan S, Gayathri R, Beatrice DA, Anjana RM, et al. Consumption pattern of millets among South Indian adults. J Diabetol. 2024; 15:63-69.